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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИМУННОГО ОТВЕТА ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ СЕРДЦА ПРИ ВНЕБОЛЬНИЧНОЙ ПНЕВМОНИИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Выяснить, чем отличается иммунный статус больных внебольничной пневмонией (ВП) и сочетанной ишемической болезнью сердца (ИБС) и как это влияет на прогноз заболевания, легочно-сердечную гемодинамику и клиническое течение. Были сформированы две группы из 58 обследованных пациентов. В 1-ю группу (средний возраст 62–10 лет) вошли 43 пациента с ВП (74%), у которых также имелись клинически значимые сопутствующие ССЗ 2-ю группу составили

Ключевые слова: Внебольничная пневмония, коморбидная сердечно-сосудистая патология, ишемическая болезнь сердца, провосполительные цитокины, легочно-сердечная гемодинамика.

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YURAK QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARI BILAN O'G'RIGAN BEMORLAR SHIFOXONADAN TASHQARI ZOTILJAMGA CHALINGANDA ULARNING IMMUN XOLATINING HUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Shifoxonadan tashqari pnevmoniya (ShTP) va yurak ishemik kasalligi (YulK) bilan og'rigan bemorlarning immun holati qanday farq qilishini va bu kasallikning prognozi, o'pka gemodinamikasi va klinikasiga qanday ta'sir qilishini aniqlash.

Tekshiruvdan o'tgan 58 nafar bemordan iborat ikkita guruh tuzildi. 1-guruhga (o'rtacha yoshi 62-10 yosh) ShTP bilan og'rigan 43 bemor (74%), shuningdek, yondosh yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bo'lgan. 2-guruh 15 bemordan iborat (o'rtacha yoshi 56±15 yil) ShTP (26%), lekin yondosh kasalliklari yo'q.

Kalit so'zlar: Shifoxonadan tashqari pnevmoniya, yurak ishemik kasalligi, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlar, o'pka-yurak gemodinamikasi.

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FEATURES OF THE IMMUNE RESPONSE OF PATIENTS WITH ISCHAEMIC HEART DISEASE IN COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA

ANNOTATION

The aim of this study was to determine how the immune status of patients with community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) and concomitant coronary heart disease (CHD) differs and how this affects the prognosis of the disease, pulmonary-cardiac hemodynamics and clinical course. Two groups of 58 patients were examined. Group 1 (average age 62–10 years) included 43 patients with CAP (74%), who also had clinically significant concomitant CVDs; group 2 consisted of

Key words: Community-acquired pneumonia, comorbid cardiovascular pathology, coronary heart disease, proinflammatory cytokines, pulmonary-cardiac hemodynamics.

After cardiovascular, cerebrovascular and malignant neoplasms occur, community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) remains one of the most urgent diseases [1]. In Uzbekistan, 3.9 deaths per 1,000 people per year are registered among persons older than 18 years [2]. From 25 to 44 cases per 1000 people per year, this rate increases significantly for persons older than 70 years. An inevitable risk factor for the unfavorable course and prognosis of CAP is concomitant cardiovascular pathology, especially in the aggravation of chronic heart failure.

In the pathogenesis of CAP, the reactivity of the immune system is crucial and primarily refers to the state of localised nonspecific lung defense. An adequate immune response requires a certain level of cytokines. In most cases, the set of bioactive substances in the blood is quite limited, and the regulatory effect is restricted to individual inhibitors. As the pathological process progresses, the quantity and quality of cytokines with near and far regulatory activity increase [4].

It is well known that CAP has a complex and protracted course due to immune system disorders preventing an adequate immune response [4]. In addition, information on the state of the immune response during the inflammatory process in different groups of patients with CAP is scattered and requires additional research. In this regard, it is important to study cytokines that control the intensity and duration of the immune response, as well as the type of inflammation, because they can both positively and negatively regulate immunity [5-7]. According to Paats

(2013), systemic levels of interleukin-6 and IL-10 are significantly greater in patients with severe CAP than in patients with nonsevere CAP and are significantly correlated with the severity of pneumonia [8]. Several authors have shown that IL-1, -6, -10 and tumor necrosis factor levels increase significantly with increasing severity of CAP.

It was previously found that the concentrations of some cytokines depend on the cause of CAP. Consequently, increased expression of IL-12 is observed in diseases caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*.

However, the extent to which important cytokines, such as IL-8 and -17, and inflammatory proteins, such as myeloperoxidase (MPO) and eosinophil cationic protein (ECP), play a role in the complex immunopathogenesis of CAP caused by cardiovascular disease (CVD) is unknown and needs further investigation.

As a result, the proinflammatory cytokine IL-17 plays a crucial role in activating the neutrophil-mediated defense response and inducing neutrophils to remove bacterial agents, both of which can be observed even in the absence of specific antibodies. In addition, IL-17 plays a role in generating a specific antibody response to *Streptococcus pneumoniae* invasion, which is the most frequent cause of pneumonia.

In this regard, it will undoubtedly become easier to predict the trajectory of CAP even in patients with concomitant CVD, as new and more effective laboratory methods for assessing the severity of the course of CAP and immune status disorders are developed. Therefore,

continuing research on the impact of proinflammatory cytokines and immune homeostasis on the progression and outcome of CAP, especially in CVD, is highly important.

Purpose of the study: To determine the specificity of immune status in CAP patients with combined cardiovascular pathology and its influence on disease prognosis, pulmonary-cardiac hemodynamics and clinical course.

Materials and methods

Fifty-eight CAP patients (mean age 60 ± 18 years), including 30 men (mean age 60 ± 12 years) and 28 women (mean age 55 ± 18 years), were examined. All patients were hospitalised in the pulmonary department, confirmed radiologically and divided into 2 groups. Group 1 included 43 CAP patients (74%) with clinically significant cardiovascular pathology (mean age 62 ± 10 years). Group 2 consisted of 15 CAP patients (26%) without comorbidities (mean age 56 ± 15 years).

The main complaints, duration of the current disease, anamnesis, presence or absence of concomitant pathology, vaccinations against influenza and pneumococcal infection, and physical data were analysed when interviewing patients. Clinical blood tests and serum biochemical studies were performed. The etiological classification of pneumonias was determined by bacteriological, virological and serological methods.

All patients had blood samples tested for pneumococcal bacteraemia by real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and nasopharyngeal swabs by real-time reverse transcription PCR (Rotor-Gene 6000, Corbett Research, Australia) using a PCR kit. The following virological tests were used: "AmpliSense Influenza A/B-FL", "AmpliSense Influenza A-FL", and "AmpliSense ARVI-screen-FRT". All patients at admission and after the course of treatment underwent X-ray imaging of the lungs in frontal and lateral projections on a QXR-9 digital radiographic apparatus (Viewworks, China). Capillary oxygen saturation determined by pulse oximetry (SpO₂) was measured in all patients. The severity of the disease and risk of mortality were determined by factors determining the place of treatment, number of diagnostic procedures and management tactics; these factors were assessed by the CRB-65 scale using 4 criteria: impaired consciousness (confusion), serum urea nitrogen (urea), respiratory rate, blood pressure and patient age (≥ 65 years).

Cytokine (IL-6, IL-8, and IL-17) and MPO levels in the serum of CAP patients at admission were studied via quantitative ELISA via standard test systems.

Central hemodynamics were studied by Doppler echocardiography using an expert-class ultrasound diagnostic system, GEVIDID 7 Dimension (General Electric, USA), and a 2-4 MHz matrix multifrequency transducer. The study was performed in M-mode and B-mode. The main indices characterising overall left and right heart function were calculated according to the recommendations of the European Society of Cardiology and the European Respiratory Society (2015).

Results and discussion

The severity of the course of CAP was determined by the CRB-65 scale. The mean score was 1.71 in the first group of patients and 1.40 ($p < 0.05$) in the second group of patients, which indicated a more severe course of the disease and effective hospitalisation for patients with CVD.

The intoxication syndrome was less pronounced when evaluating the clinical data on hospitalisation of the first group of patients. The mean body temperature was $38.1 \pm 1.2^\circ\text{C}$, whereas it was $38.8 \pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$ ($p < 0.05$) in patients with CAP without CVD. The time from symptom onset to hospitalisation was 12 ± 4 days in patients with CVD compared with 6 ± 4 days in patients without concomitant CVD; i.e., in group 1 patients, clinical symptoms developed gradually, resulting in a late diagnosis (72 hours or more after the first symptoms appeared).

According to the bacteriological study of sputum, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was isolated from 7% ($n=4$) of patients, *Staphylococcus aureus* was isolated from 9% ($n=5$), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was isolated from 2% ($n=1$) of the unicellular bacteria. In 45% ($n=26$) of the patients, the concentration of microorganisms was clinically insignificant, and no increase in pathological microbial flora was detected in 34% ($n=20$) of the patients. However, the results of a

published international study conducted in Europe in 2005-2012 showed that *Streptococcus pneumoniae* causes CAP in 12.0-85.0% of patients, and in the present study, this pathogen was detected in only 1 patient (2%). Real-time PCR did not detect pneumococci in the blood of any of the examined patients.

When examining nasopharyngeal swabs, viruses were isolated from 11 patients: influenza A/H3N2 virus in 3 (27%), respiratory syncytial virus in 2 (18%), rhinovirus in 4 (37%), rhinovirus in 2 (18%), and coronaviruses.

In group 1 patients at the time of admission, since most patients had no productive cough and the sputum samples obtained were contaminated with oropharyngeal microorganisms, the etiological diagnosis was limited, and only 4 patients (9%) were likely to have infectious agents when bacteriological examination of sputum revealed *Staphylococcus aureus* in 2 patients, influenza A virus in 1 patient and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in 1 patient.

Radiological data from CVD patients revealed a predominance of pathological processes (86%) localised in the lower lobe, half of which (49%) were on both sides.

The comparative data of the mean values of the general blood analyses at admission are shown in Table

Note the decreased haemoglobin and increased platelet count in the first group of patients. Anaemia in these patients may be related to the overproduction of hepcidin in the liver occurring during infection and inflammation. This process is initiated by proinflammatory cytokines that interfere with iron release from macrophages and iron absorption by the intestine, resulting in hypoferrremia and anaemia during inflammation.

According to the biochemical blood analysis of group 2 patients at admission, higher C-reactive protein levels were detected. Moreover, the transaminase, glucose and creatinine levels were lower in these patients than in group 1 patients, which could be associated with a more pronounced systemic response to infectious changes.

Moreover, there was no significant difference in the mean fibrinogen level or activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) between the two groups.

Compared to those in the second group, the prothrombin index and international normalised ratio (INR) were greater in the first group of CAP patients, indicating the instability of blood coagulation. Since the INR is inversely proportional to plasma clotting time, i.e., the higher the INR is and the less prothrombin and clotting factors there are in plasma, an increase in the INR may have a positive effect on the course of combined CVD in the first group of patients.

When comparing the serum IL-6 indices of the studied groups, the level of this cytokine increased 2.3 times in patients in the second group (Table 1). IL-6 characterises the lack of an adequate response of the adaptive immune system and causes an acute inflammatory reaction associated with cytokine hyperexpression in the liver, which is manifested by increased synthesis of acute phase proteins (C-reactive protein, fibrinogen, serum amyloid A, α -antitrypsin and haptoglobin) and impaired lipid and lipoprotein metabolism—independent predictors of cardiovascular complications. Thus, low IL-6 production in patients in the first group could additionally favourably affect the functional state of the cardiovascular system, whereas the increased level of this index in patients in the second group created conditions for this. Possible undesirable complications for the cardiovascular system.

The average level of IL-8 in the second group of patients was almost twice as high as that in the first group. In the second group of patients, the increase in cytokine levels was characterised by a pronounced inflammatory reaction in which heparinized venous blood was collected from 14 conditionally healthy donors aged 21 to 35 years, as determined by ELISA. IL-8 is involved in the mechanism regulating long-term immune memory, which leads to the directed migration of neutrophils and lymphocytes to inflammatory processes. An increase in the level of IL-8 in the second group of patients was associated with a more pronounced incidence of toxic syndrome upon admission.

Correlation analysis of the second group of patients revealed a direct strong and reliable relationship between IL-8 and the INR ($r=0.85$, $p < 0.05$); namely, the more pronounced the inflammatory process was, the more significant the difference in the INR and the lower the

prothrombin and clotting factor levels were, which in turn favourably affects the functional state of the cardiovascular system.

The mean IL-17 concentration in the first group of patients was almost twice as high as that in the second group. The increase in cytokine levels in the first group of patients was mainly due to the development of inflammation, albeit slowly. These patients at admission had weakly expressed intoxication syndrome and slow development of clinical symptoms, and the levels of the acute phase proteins inflammation and IL-6 were lower than those in the other group of patients. Second, the increased cytokine levels in group 1 patients were associated with the presence of comorbid CVD, the formation and development of which are associated with the important role of IL-17, significantly aggravating the course of concomitant pathology.

When studying the correlation between IL-17 levels and inflammatory markers in the serum of Group 1 patients, it was found that there was a strong direct and reliable correlation between elevated IL-17 levels and the levels of neutrophils and inflammatory markers. New forms of leukocytes ($r=0.85$ and $r=0.91$, $p<0.05$) suggest a key role for this cytokine in the defense of organisms against extracellular bacteria.

Calculation of the correlations between cytokine levels and the INR and echocardiographic parameters in group 1 patients revealed a direct, moderately strong correlation between serum IL-17 levels and the time to maximal ejection. There was an almost strong correlation with the velocity of the right ventricular outflow tract and a direct strong correlation with the diameter of the inferior vena cava. In the first group of patients, IL-17 contributed to the development of pulmonary hypertension (increase in pulmonary artery systolic pressure up to 43 ± 13.0 mmHg). All of the above findings may provide evidence that elevated IL-17 contributes to the development of right ventricular failure in CAP patients with CVD. Massachusetts studies support this. Saleh (2016), who found that the inhibition of IL-17 signalling by monoclonal antibodies directed against IL-17A or IL-17RA, reduced systolic blood pressure by 30 mmHg. Orehudo (2020) suggested that IL-17A is involved in the development of autoimmune chronic inflammatory processes and CVD, mainly through the regulation of proinflammatory cytokines. In addition, this cytokine may play an important role in the regulation of systemic arterial pressure, arteriolar remodelling and stiffness. The mechanism of action of IL-17A is associated with the development of hypertrophy of smooth muscle fibres in the vascular wall and phenotypic changes in the absence of extracellular matrix proteins. It can be assumed that against the background of initial decompensation of the right ventricle in these

patients, an immune response due to activation of the IL-17 system develops. However, the role of IL-17 in the development of vascular wall damage and the irreversibility of the pathological process remain controversial.

When calculating the correlations between the MPO level and echocardiographic parameters in Group 1 patients, a direct strong correlation with the left ventricular eccentricity index and a negative, almost strong correlation with the inferior vena cava diameter were revealed. MPO is a neutrophil lysosomal enzyme that has a nonspecific bactericidal effect through the formation of the strong oxidising anion hypochlorite. Along with the destruction of neutrophils, the concentration of MPO gradually increases, the influence of toxic infectious factors on the myocardium weakens, the contractility begins to recover, and the stasis of the great circle of circulation and the diameter of the inferior vena cava gradually decrease. An increased MPO level creates conditions conducive to improving cardiohemodynamics.

Thus, the activity of the inflammatory process can significantly affect the state of pulmonary cardiocirculation in patients with CVD, and dynamic monitoring of changes in proinflammatory cytokines and immune homeostasis expands the possibility of assessing CAP. The functional state of pulmonary cardiohemodynamics allows timely initiation of cardioprotective therapy and monitoring of its effectiveness.

Conclusions

In patients with CAP with concomitant CVD, activation of the immune system was less pronounced than that in the other group, which was manifested by mild intoxication syndrome, a slow increase in clinical symptoms and low production of acute phase proteins and proinflammatory cytokines (IL-6, - 8). Against the background of the initial development of right ventricular decompensation, patients in the first group developed an immune response caused by activation of the IL-17 system. An increase in the level of cytokines is associated not only with the development of inflammatory processes but also with the simultaneous presence of CVD. Dynamic changes in the serum IL-17 concentration in patients with CAP can be used as prognostic indicators of the severity of the pathological process and the functional state of the pulmonary circulation.

Further studies of the dynamics of the levels of proinflammatory cytokines and acute-phase proteins in patients with CAP with clinically significant CVD are promising because the goals are to develop new diagnostic methods, detect complications in a timely manner, prescribe adequate treatment and evaluate the effectiveness of treatment.

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